

COMPARISON OF VOLUMETRIC AND TWO-DIMENSIONAL IMAGE CORRELATION ON COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The presented work shows the comparison of two-dimensional digital image correlation (2D-DIC) with the results of volumetric digital image correlation (V-DIC) of in situ micro-computer tomographic (μ CT) testing and its use for material modeling. The aim is to compare the results of the strains from both imaging correlation methods and to analyze the difference between the strains on the outer surface and the inner volume of the composite specimen.

Testing is conducted within a μ CT device while performing the strain measurement during loading with a single camera system from the outside of the μ CT. The load is applied in different load steps to generate a steady state necessary for μ CT-imaging. Both captured imaging methods (the 2D-measurement as well as the volumetric images) are investigated by means of digital image correlation methods.

The testing results are evaluated mainly on two aspects: Firstly, it was investigated how close the results of V-DIC and 2D-DIC are in the steady state at the surface. This gives an estimation of the comparability of the results and the reliability of the testing approach. Secondly, the possible differences between the strains on the outer surface of the specimen and its inner volume are investigated to see possible influences on the damage state of the composite. Both aspects are discussed within this work.

Finally a conclusion is made and further improvements for the future research work are shown.

1 INTRODUCTION

For the testing of materials, digital image correlation is an established method for measuring surface deformations and strains. An overview of the theory and the method is given in [1]. The measurement technique uses an arbitrary speckle pattern on the surface of the specimen. DIC is especially useful for anisotropic materials since it offers to measure strains directly on the prepared specimens surface. While single camera systems are available for in-plane (2D) measurements, two (or more) cameras are used for additional out of plane (3D) measurements.

Volumetric image correlation offers new possibilities for the material investigation under load. As such it is possible to use the theory of digital image correlation as depicted in [1]. Instead of the correlation of two-dimensional images, volumetric images (as for example μ CT-data) are correlated. This gives the possibility to evaluate strains within a specimen, especially, but not only for anisotropic composite materials. For the image correlation technique an arbitrary pattern is necessary. In consequence fiber reinforced plastics are suitable for investigations of volumetric strains, due to their microstructure, which offers a phase contrast of the different materials used in the composite material.

The challenges of this measurement procedure are various. First, the test bench has to be applicable to CT-measurements, meaning that a rotation of the specimen has to be allowed and that no metallic components disturb the x-ray imaging process. In his work, *Sause* [2] presents different constructional possibilities for CT in-situ test benches, also for different load scenarios. The main use is tensile testing, where several solutions are offered commercially as well as testing services from institutes and companies are available. This shows an increasing impact and demand in the evaluation of materials through μ CT-in-situ testing. Starting with a reference scan of the specimen before loading, the

measurement procedure can be described with the following loop (see also Figure 1): apply a load, stop at a defined load, wait for the material to stop creeping and finally conduct the μ CT image capturing. This procedure is repeated until specimen failure. Thereby the μ CT-scan can take up to several hours. The long image capturing time is a tradeoff to the fact that the μ CT-scan gives information about the material deformation within the specimen, which is not offered by conventional DIC where only strains on the outside are provided. Due to influential effects of the x-ray beam with the specimen (i.e. heating up of the specimen as well as the surrounding) differences exist between the surface based DIC- and the V-DIC-method. This is especially critical for temperature dependent materials as polymers and their composite derivatives. Furthermore, the repeatability of the μ CT-measurements in combination with the V-DIC has not been investigated thoroughly, possibly due to the time-consuming measurement procedure.

Figure 1: In-situ-CT measurement procedure

For the investigation of fiber-reinforced polymer materials (frp-materials) another aspect is critical: Usually the fiber orientation on the outer faces differs from the inside. This applies for multi-layer composites and injection molded parts in particular. In consequence the distributions of stress and strain vary from the outer faces to the inside of the specimen, which might lead to premature failure. In particular the damaging behavior should be investigated for rather complex fiber orientations as, for example, short fiber reinforced plastics.

The objective of this work is to compare the two measurement techniques since the overall measurement errors and the repeatability of volumetric image correlation are not well known yet. By examining the V-DIC in combination with DIC this study aims to provide knowledge about the differences of the techniques as well as their use for short-frp-materials and damaging. Through the comparison a conclusion should be made to the measurement uncertainties of the μ CT-measurements for frp-materials. The material used is a short glass fiber reinforced thermoplastic material which offers good suitability for volumetric image correlation.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

To offer the possibility for comparison of the different image correlation systems, several aspects have to be adjusted. Figure 2 shows schematically the proposed measurement setup. The central element is the *Phoenix Nanotom 180NF* μ CT manufactured by *General Electric*, containing the x-ray source, the rotary table and the x-ray detector. The chamber of the μ CT is accessible through a window (marked with a dashed line in Figure 2). The μ CT-test bench is positioned on the rotary table, on which the DIC-camera is focusing from the outside through the μ CT access window during load application. A positioning of the camera in the chamber of the μ CT is not possible due to the limited space. The control units of the systems are placed around the μ CT, with the μ CT-unit fixed, DIC- and test-bench-control units are moveable and can be placed anywhere suitable. The following paragraphs describe the specimens, the μ CT-test-bench, the DIC-system as well as the VIC-method in detail.

Figure 2: Measurement setup in a schematic view for the *Phoenix Nanotom μCT*, with μCT-components, μCT-test bench components and DIC components

2.1. Specimens

The specimens, made out of short-fiber reinforced polyamide 66 with 30 weight percent of glass fibers, are manufactured according to DIN EN ISO 527-2 [3] with the geometry of a type 1BA specimen. The specimens are cut out of an injection molded plate according to DIN EN ISO 294-5 [4] and conditioned at room climate. For the digital image correlation method the specimen preparation includes the application of an arbitrary speckle pattern. Figure 3 shows a prepared specimen. Two different fiber orientations of 0° and 90° are examined.

Figure 3: Type 1BA specimen prepared for DIC-measurements with a fiber orientation of 0°

2.2. μCT Test Setup

For in-situ testing a special test bench was developed to be applicable for the requirements in a μCT. Figure 4 shows the construction of the test bench as well as the test setup within the μCT. The main part for the force transmission is a Polymethylmethacrylat (PMMA)-cylinder. This guarantees free access for x-ray and DIC-imaging of the test specimen. Metallic components as used usually for the load transmission are causing measurement errors due to their high absorbance of x-rays. The top and bottom part of the test bench are manufactured from steel and mounted to the PMMA-cylinder. Both parts contain clamping areas for the specimen. The load cell (up to 2 kN maximum) is placed at the bottom section which stays fixed during testing. The top section contains the moveable clamps, guided linear driven through a spindle drive. The displacement is measured with an inductive proximity sensor. The whole fixture is designed to fit exactly in the *Phoenix Nanotom μCT*.

Testing is conducted at a speed of 0.02 mm/s and stopped stepwise in load increments of 400N, using a displacement-controlled system. The testing standard used is DIN EN ISO 527 [3, 5].

Figure 4: Construction of the μ CT test bench (on the left) and test setup mounted in the *Phoenix μ CT* (on the right)

2.2 Digital Image Correlation System

As DIC-system serves an *Aramis* measurement system manufactured by *gom GmbH* at a variable base, allowing for adjustment to different experimental setups. Two camera (3D-DIC) as well as single camera (2D-DIC) measurements are possible. Usually 3D-measurements are conducted, because of the additional information about out-of-plane deformations. For 3D-DIC measurements however, a calibration with the given setup is not possible. Further the needed lighting for the image capturing causes reflections, which can be much easier avoided by the use of only a single camera. Finally, the PMMA-cylinder causes potentially measurement errors due to the curvature and local defects (i.e. surface scratches) and in consequence distortion of the speckle-pattern in these areas, which might be varying seen from different camera angles. In-plane deformations can be evaluated with only one camera (2D-DIC), which is chosen for the current setup, avoiding the problems given for 3D-DIC.

2.3 Volumetric image correlation system

The core of the system is the *Phoenix Nanotom 180NF* μ CT as depicted in Figure 2. The resolution of the system can be adjusted to the specimen and the volume to be examined. Resolution and magnification depend on the the distance from the x-ray source to the object and the distance from the object to the detector. Best spatial resolutions (typically described in $\mu\text{m}/\text{voxel}$) are given for a close position of the specimen to the x-ray source and a long distance between the specimen and the detector. Thereby it has to be considered that the volume to be investigated is directly dependent to the spatial resolution, At the current state the resolution is limited to $10.7 \mu\text{m}/\text{voxel}$ through the setup with the cylindrical test bench, which does not allow for a closer position of the specimen to the x-ray source. In this casethe full specimen is scanned.

X-ray-imaging is conducted every 0.2 degree of the rotation of the test bench with a total measurement time of approximately two and a half hours. After the scanning is finalized the reconstruction of the area of interest of the specimen can be conducted which serves as input data for

the volumetric image correlation. Only the tapered section of the specimen is investigated. Due to the long scanning time only one scan as reference and one at each load step have been taken.

Volumetric image correlation uses the same theory as for digital image correlation, only now executed on volumetric images, as for example μ CT-scans. Thereby the needed arbitrary speckle pattern has to be given through the microstructure of the specimen to investigate. Short-fiber-reinforced thermoplastics, especially filled with glass-fibers, give a good contrast as well as the arbitrary pattern by their short fiber length and the varying fiber orientation through the thickness of the injection-molded specimen. *VicVolumeTM* from *Correlated Solutions INC, USA* provided by *isi-sys GmbH Germany* serves as the computational software, offering the possibility to calculate the strains within the examined specimen.

3 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

With the use of three independent systems the experimental routine follows complex structures and gives various possibilities for errors. To minimize the risk of errors the measurements have to be conducted at a defined procedure oriented on the measurement loop for V-DIC (Figure 1). The additional use of the 2D-DIC-system is restricted to load application and material creeping (until reaching a steady force). For this purpose a programmed image capturing is used to adjust the data-acquisition to the needed information. The image capturing frequency starts at 2 Hertz in the beginning of the test and ending at 0.1 Hertz. Details are presented in Table 1, where the sections succeed each other directly. During CT-scanning of the specimen 2D-DIC is not applicable due to the closed chamber with camera positioned on the exterior.

Table 1: Image capturing frequencies of the 2D-DIC system, time periods and overall images

Section	Frequency (Hz)	Time period (s)	Overall images
1	2	300	600
2	1	600	1200
3	0,2	1200	1440
4	0,1	Open	Open

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Experimental results

Overall one specimen with 0°-fiber orientation at three load levels and one with 90° fiber-orientation at two load levels were investigated up to now. A major difference to the proposed measurement procedure in Figure 2 is that for the 2D-DIC measurements the μ CT-test bench has to be removed from the μ -CT-chamber. Restricted through the limited space inside and around the μ CT the measurements were not possible at the contemplated position. In consequence a rigid and consistent positioning of the μ CT-test bench was used for the load application and simultaneously 2D-DIC-measurements. Repositioning of the test bench in the μ CT was taking place at same conditions.

The results are investigated to evaluate the differences between DIC and VIC. Unfortunately, only two of the load steps were running without any interference in the complex measuring setup, one for each specimen. Interferences mean hereby any deviation from the adjusted measurements (i.e. interruption of the CT-scan or problems in the repositioning of the μ CT-test bench). Reasoned by the vast information of the measurements these two load steps were investigated in detail. Figure 5 shows the plot of the stress-strain curve for the 0°-specimen when applying the third load step of approximately 1200 N. The stress is given by the force divided by the undeformed cross-sectional area (before any type of loading). Strains are calculated as the mean-value of the respective areas of interest for 2D-DIC and V-DIC, which are located in the same specimen region. The V-DIC results are investigated close to the 2D-DIC prepared surface (in-situ surface marked in yellow in Figure 5) at the mid-plane of the specimen (marked in black) and the far-plane opposite to the prepared surface

(marked in red). The V-DIC values can only be evaluated at the constant load level. Therefore, these need to be compared to the end of the stress-strain-curve determined by 2D-DIC.

Figure 5: Stress-strain curve of the 0° -specimen at the third load step compared to the V-DIC close to the specimen's surface, at the mid-plane and at the far-plane (position seen from the 2D-DIC measurement)

At the depicted third load level plastic deformations occur already. After a short linear section the slope of the curves degrades continuously. At a value of approximately 352.5 N for the load step, 33.6 MPa respectively, loading is stopped. At this point creeping and relaxation of the material starts, with stress and strain decreasing. After 90 minutes dwell time the 2D-DIC measurement is stopped and the μ CT-test bench is repositioned for the μ CT-scan in the chamber. Based on this scan and the final scan of the second load step of the specimen *VicVolumeTM* is used for the V-DIC evaluation. The results of the V-DIC thereby are close to the final result of the 2D-DIC as depicted in Figure 5 and summarized in Table 2. All values calculated by *VicVolumeTM* are slightly lower than the 2D-DIC value of approximately 0.59 percent. This can also be observed for the standard deviation, except for the V-DIC mid-plane measurement which has the lowest value of 0.097 percent, the other values ranging from 0.147 percent for 2D-DIC and from 0.160 to 0.185 for the other VIC-values. Thereby the standard deviation is calculated as an absolute value in respect to the mean value. Relative values are depicted in the third row of Table 1. Here the standard deviation can be rated as high with peak values of 32 percent of the mean-value. These can be influenced by the input parameters of the algorithm as well as the filter, which is used traditionally for DIC calculations.

Table 2: Results of the tensile strains ϵ_{yy} for 2D-DIC with VIC at different cross-sections of the specimen

Strain ϵ_{yy}	Mean-value [%]	standard deviation [%]	standard deviation relative to mean value
2D-DIC	0.5873	0.14684	0.2500
<i>VicVolume</i> Surface	0.5717	0.18501	0.3236
<i>VicVolume</i> mid-plane	0.5656	0.09721	0.1719
<i>VicVolume</i> far-plane	0.5636	0.16014	0.2841

4.2 Conclusions

The presented work shows a concept for the comparison of two image correlation systems, 2D-DIC and VIC, respectively. Both setups use completely different technologies although the algorithm theory and basics stay consistent. DIC is an easy and fast accessible system frequently applied in material and component testing. Due to the use of μ CT the V-DIC-method instead is generally slow and can only be conducted at distinctive load levels, with a specific test bench. However it generates information about strains within the volume of the investigated specimen. This possibility is not offered by any other measurement method yet. Due to the similarity of the DIC and V-DIC approaches this work investigates the measurement differences of the respective methods. For this purpose, two short glass frp specimens were investigated which are especially suitable for VIC.

The acquired data hints at a good comparability of the methods, where in a first step the mean-values are examined. The final result of 2D-DIC is in close range to the VIC-data, although the standard deviation relative to the mean-values is high. Depending on the specimen and load step this might be caused by local yield and thus peaks in the local strains, next to the input parameters of the DIC- or VIC algorithms, which are having an influence on the standard deviation. In further investigations a more detailed and local comparison of the data is planned.

With respect to the measurement and data acquisition the complex setup of three independent systems (μ CT, test-bench and 2D-DIC) lead to varying uncertainties or measurement interruptions. One major factor was the extraction of the μ CT-test bench necessary for load application and 2D-DIC. In the near future this should be avoided through adaptation of the 2D-DIC system such that the extraction of the test bench is not required anymore. Other factors are the energy input of the x-ray system, which could not be investigated in detail yet. The needed power of the x-rays is at the top range of the *Phoenix Nanotom* μ CT since it is necessary to radiograph the specimen and the PMMA-cylinder in addition. In consequence the energy input is at a very high level. During the scan an inconsistent force could be observed at the load cell. The reason for this might vary from the thermal expansion of the test bench or the temperature dependent material behavior of the polymeric materials (specimen and PMMA-cylinder). Detailed information about these influences is not yet possible with the given setup. Overall, two load steps were running smoothly and five with interferences. Adjustments, as for example the DIC measurements within the CT, are going to be taken to guarantee a higher output of the experiments. In consequence statistics of these measurements could not be evaluated and more experiments are needed.

Finally, subsequent improvements of the experimental process chain are planned, starting with the adjustments of the 2D-DIC to measure with the test bench in the μ CT and the construction of a new test bench especially designed for these experimental purposes and eliminating constraints caused by the given setup (i.e. resolution of the μ CT-scan). Further experiments are planned on drilled-hole specimens to investigate details on the damaging behavior of short-fiber-reinforced plastics.

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